

A Prospective Study of Clinical and Etiological Profile of Fever of Unknown Origin in Children

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Abstract

Background: Fever of unknown origin (FUO) is a common presentation in the pediatric age group worldwide. The spectrum of illness changes from one geographic location to another and also varies at different times. The current study aimed to study the clinical and etiological profile of children aged 2 months to 12 years admitted for more than 2 weeks with fevers of unknown origin in a tertiary care hospital.

Methods: This cross-sectional observational study was conducted in the Department of Pediatrics. FUO was described as a fever greater than 100.4°F lasting at least 8 days in patients without a definitive diagnosis after an initial assessment in the outpatient clinic or the hospital. A thorough history, including travel history, was obtained from all patients. This was followed by a detailed general and systemic examination, repeated daily to identify potential etiological clues. Clinical and biochemical data were recorded systematically using a structured proforma. The initial investigations included Complete blood count (CBC) with erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), Peripheral blood smear, Urinalysis, Routine biochemistry, Chest X-ray, Urine, stool, and blood cultures.

Results: A total of 85 cases were included in the study based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Infections caused by bacterial pathogens accounted for 52.9% of cases in this study followed by Rickettsial pathogens were the most common in the group, accounting for 24.7%. Scrub typhus was the leading cause, identified in 21 out of 70 (30.0%) patients in the infectious group. Among bacterial infections, enteric fever (23.5%), Pneumonia (10.6%), UTI (9.4%), and sepsis (5.9%) were predominant. Malaria was diagnosed in 2 cases (2.3%) using rapid malarial card tests (LDH-based) and confirmed by thin and thick smear analysis.

Conclusions: Within the limitations of the current study we concluded that infections were the primary cause of FUO in children with enteric fever and scrub typhus being the most frequent diagnosis. Early identification of the cause through specific investigations and appropriate antimicrobial treatment in bacterial diseases will be beneficial.

Keywords: Fever of Unknown Origin (FUO), Enteric Fever, Scrub typhus.

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Introduction

Fever in children is a common phenomenon however it can increase parental anxiety. Pediatricians are under constant pressure to identify the case. A fever of unknown origin (FUO) is said to be present when the fever persists for more than two weeks without any underlying cause that could be identified. The term FUO was first introduced by Petersdorf and Beeson who had coined this term in adults with temperatures exceeding 38.3°C on multiple occasions and persisting for more than three weeks and diagnosis remained elusive after one week of hospital-based investigations [1]. Several studies have been conducted on FUO in different regions across the world and in different age groups [2-4]. The important findings of these

studies reveal the etiology was different in different regions based on geographical locations, socio-economic conditions, and seasonal conditions [5-7]. In pediatric cases, there is an additional challenge due to practical difficulties in children repeatedly obtaining blood, urine, or sputum samples. Since pediatric patients are more vulnerable as their limited ability to communicate symptoms complicates the diagnostic process.

It is important to recognize that the causes of FUO are not uniform across the globe—or even within a single province. They differ based on geography, socioeconomic status, ethnicity, seasonality, healthcare facilities, immunization coverage, diagnostic advancements, antibiotic policies, and

hygienic practices. Regions with poor sanitation, limited healthcare access, and inconsistent vaccination programs often report infections as a leading cause of FUO [5, 8]. Conversely, in regions with advanced healthcare systems, autoimmune diseases, malignancies, and other non-infectious causes might dominate. In the last few decades, diagnostic tools, including molecular methods, improved imaging studies, and next-generation sequencing, have advanced leading to better-FUO etiology determination [7, 9]. However, the problem of FUO has not disappeared even with these sophisticated tools, especially in developing countries where such tools are hardly available. That is why the appearance of antimicrobial resistance complicates the treatment of FUO even more as empirical treatment loses its efficacy [10]. Among all age groups, children can be best described as vulnerable to these infections and inflammatory conditions thanks to their immunological system. Furthermore, patients especially children may present a different picture of illness and fever than the adults making it hard for the doctor to determine the cause of the illness. Such infections can be tuberculosis, typhoid, viral diseases, and many others may manifest in children with symptoms that are different from those seen in adults. Such variations stress the fact that an organized approach to assessing FUO with reference to epidemiological characteristics of different regions should be followed [11].

The literature review of prior studies reveals that there is a research gap more specifically in Indian children and in this region, to understand satisfyingly the etiology of FUO [12]. Although information concerning previous years may have been quite useful, alterations in healthcare delivery systems, increased vaccination, and enhanced standard hygiene might alter the level of FUO in recent years. This study will therefore fill this gap by assessing the current etiologic predispositions to FUO in children within our locality. Knowledge of these patterns is valuable for designing diagnostic decision trees, and empirical treatment, and for enhancing patients' survival rates.

Material and Methods

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted in the Department of Pediatrics, GMC Wanaparthy, Telangana. Institutional Ethical approval was obtained for the study. Written consent was obtained from the parents of the children included in the study after explaining the nature of the study in vernacular language. The main aim of the study was to find out the cause and the prognosis of FUO. Secondary aims included establishing whether the clinician can identify the cause in all patients using the available diagnostic tools and finding whether there is a relationship between the clinical presentation and the underlying etiology.

FUO was described as a fever greater than 101.0°F lasting a minimum of 8 days in patients who had not received a definitive diagnosis after an initial assessment in the outpatient clinic or the hospital [1]. This is one of the widely accepted clinical definitions of FUO in pediatric practice as well as practice in general.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged from 2 months to 12 years
2. Males and females
3. had a fever >100.4°F for eight or more days.
4. Admitted to our hospital
5. Parents willing to participate in the study voluntarily

Exclusion Criteria

1. Immunocompromised patients
2. Children with documented recurrent fever
3. Periodic fever syndromes.
4. Not willing to participate in the study

A thorough history, including travel history, was obtained from all patients. This was followed by a detailed general and systemic examination, repeated daily to identify potential etiological clues. Clinical and biochemical data were recorded systematically using a structured proforma. The initial investigations included Complete blood count (CBC) with erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), Peripheral blood smear, Urinalysis, Routine biochemistry, Chest X-ray, Urine, stool, and blood cultures. Additional tests were done when required which included Serological tests for bacterial and viral infections, Tuberculin skin tests, Immunological markers (e.g., ANA, C3, C4, C-ANCA), HIV testing, Imaging studies like abdominal or lymph node ultrasound, contrast CT, or MRI, and Echocardiography.

Invasive Procedures

Invasive investigations, such as lumbar puncture, analysis of pleural or ascitic fluid, lymph node aspiration/excision, bone marrow aspiration, and liver biopsy, were performed when indicated by clinical findings or initial test results.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis of research results was carried out using the software package of statistical analysis of results of studies SPSS 22.0 (IBM SPSS, US). The continuous variables were represented as mean, standard deviation, and percentage. To test the differences between categorical variables the chi-square test has been used, and the level of significance was established at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Table 1 shows the distribution of FUO cases categorized based on age. A total of 85 cases were

included in the study based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The majority of the cases were seen in the 3-12 years age group, with 54.1% of the total. The distribution of cases was even more or less in all groups. The mean age of the cohort was 6.8 years, and the range of cases was 2 months to 12 years. The age group of 3-5 years had the highest percentage (36.5 %) of all cases. The second most

affected age group was the 10-12 years age group (23.5%). The lowest proportion of employees leaving work early was in the 2-month to 1-year age group, at 1.2%. The higher FUI incidence in the 3 to 12-year-old age group could be due to several reasons, including increased exposure to infections, minor changes in the immune system, or chronic illnesses.

Table 1: Age-wise distribution of cases of FUI included in the study

Age group	Male	Female	Total
2 months – 1 year	1 (1.8%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.2%)
1 – 3 years	5 (9.1%)	2 (6.7%)	7 (8.2%)
3 – 5 years	20 (36.4%)	11 (36.7%)	31 (36.5%)
5 – 10 years	16 (29.1%)	10 (23.3%)	26 (30.6%)
10 – 12 years	13 (23.6%)	7 (23.3%)	20 (23.5%)
Total	55 (100.0%)	30 (100.0%)	85 (100.0%)

In this study the duration of fever was recorded in all the cases we found that the majority of cases (87%) experienced a fever duration of 10-14 days (Figure 1). A significant minority (13%) had a fe-

ver lasting more than 14 days. The mean fever duration was 9.5 days, indicating a moderate course of illness. Hospital stays ranged from 4 to 30 days, with an average of 6.5 days.

Figure 1: Showing the duration of fever in cases of FUI in the study

Table 2 depicts the causes identified by diagnosis in cases of FUI included in the study. We found that infectious diseases were the most common cause of FUI, accounting for 70 (82.4%) cases. Enteric fever and urinary tract infections (UTIs) were the most frequent bacterial infections identified. Rickettsial infections, particularly scrub typhus, were the leading cause of viral FUI. While less common, malignancies (primarily acute leukemias) and autoimmune diseases (like systemic lupus erythematosus) were identified in a few cases. A significant proportion of cases (12.9%) remained undiagnosed despite extensive investigations. Infections caused by bacterial pathogens accounted

for 52.9% of cases in this study followed by Rickettsial pathogens were the most common in the group, accounting for 24.7%, Scrub typhus was the leading cause, identified in 21 out of 70 (30.0%) patients in the infectious group. Among bacterial infections, enteric fever (23.5%), Pneumonia (10.6%), UTI (9.4%), and sepsis (5.9%) were predominant. Malaria was diagnosed in 2 cases (2.3%) using rapid malarial card tests (LDH-based) and confirmed by thin and thick smear analysis by a trained microbiologist. These included 1 case of *Plasmodium vivax* and 1 case of *Plasmodium falciparum*. Hepatitis A was the common viral infection, presenting as FUI (2.3% of cases).

Table 2: Showing the diagnosis in cases of FUO included in the study

		Diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Infectious diseases (70)	Bacterial (45)	Enteric Fever	20	23.5
		UTI	8	9.4
		Sepsis	5	5.9
		Abdominal wall abscess	3	3.5
		Pneumonia	9	10.6
	Rickettsial (21)	Scrub Typhus	21	24.7
	Viral (2)	Hepatitis A	2	2.3
Parasitic (2)	Malaria	2	2.3	
	Malignancy (3)	Acute lymphoblastic leukemia	2	2.3
Acute myelogenous leukemia		1	1.2	
Autoimmune Disease (1)	SLE	1	1.2	
Undiagnosed (11)			11	12.9

The symptoms documented in FUO cases in the study are highlighted in the table below; (Table 3). Symptoms such as chills, rigors, vomiting, poor appetite, and rash were noted in many animals, regardless of the overall diagnostic groupings; thus, they could not be used to separate animals based on their disease. Fever, chills, rigors, and malaise are common symptoms of both bacterial and viral in-

fective endocarditis. Commonly reported malignant symptoms include fever, weight loss, and fatigue, all of which are associated with an underlying systemic disease. In the undiagnosed group, the subjects exhibited a broad spectrum of clinical signs, which confirmed the challenges in making the diagnosis in some cases.

Table 3: Showing the clinical presentation in different diagnosed cases of FUO

Clinical presentation	Bacterial (35)	Rickettsial (31)	Viral (2)	Parasitic (2)	Malignancy (3)	Autoimmune disease (1)	Undiagnosed (11)
Chills and rigors	30	30	1	2	2	1	5
Vomiting	5	5	1	0	1	0	1
Poor appetite	10	4	0	1	0	0	4
Pallor	9	1	0	0	1	1	2
Rash	10	1	1	1	2	0	0
Lymphadenopathy	2	2	0	0	0	0	4
Myalgia	2	0	1	1	1	0	1
Fatigue	6	2	0	1	1	0	1
Splenomegaly	3	2	1	1	1	1	1

The FUO presentation in the cases of our study was found to be wide ranged. Despite the complex presentation, all the cases in the study were successfully diagnosed, treated, and discharged. Most of the undiagnosed cases underwent spontaneous resolution after which they were discharged from the hospital. There was no reported mortality in the cases of this study.

Discussion

This cross-sectional study showed that infections are the most common etiological factor for FUO in children aged 1–12 years in this region of South India. The results of this study indicated that the

most common cause of FUO was infectious diseases, among which bacterial infections were most frequently followed closely by rickettsial scrub typhus infection in 24.7% of cases. Previous studies evaluating FUO have also demonstrated that infections are the most common cause of FUO. In a similar study by Joshi et al. [12] infections were found to be the predominant cause of FUO, with enteric fever being the most common (16.47 %). Kejriwal et al. [13] studied FUO in adults and found that the predominant cause of FUO was tuberculosis in 53% of the cases, followed by neoplasms in 17%, and 14% of the cases remained undiagnosed. The incidence of undiagnosed cases in our study was 12.9%, which is in agreement with the study by

Kejriwal et al. [12] and Mir T et al. [14] in their study also found FUO was most commonly caused by enteric fever in 32.3% of cases. Therefore, all cases of FUO must undergo a widal test to detect *Salmonella typhi* infections. One of the important reasons for increased enteric fever in India is inadequate sanitation and poor hygiene, which is especially prevalent in rural areas. Most cases in this study responded to intravenous ceftriaxone therapy. The incidence of scrub typhus in this study was 24.7% of all infections, which is comparatively higher than that reported in similar studies. This could be attributed to the geographic location and months of the year in which the cases were observed. Scrub typhus particularly increases during rainy seasons. Moreover, it remains underdiagnosed or closely mimics other tropical infections, such as leptospirosis and dengue fever.

In our study, eschar was observed in 14 of 21 cases (66.7%). While the presence of an eschar strongly supports the diagnosis of scrub typhus, its absence does not rule it out. There are studies that show wide variations in eschar prevalence, as low as 9.5% in the study by Sharma et al. [15] and as high as 89% in the study by Premaratna et al. [16]. Eschar tends to remain undetected if occurs in concealed areas such as the axilla or groin. Eschar may also go unnoticed unless specifically searched for in concealed areas such as the axilla and groin. The higher proportion of diagnosed cases in our study can be attributed to the anticipation of scrub typhus as a cause of FUO and the availability of serological tests at our center. The gold standard for scrub typhus diagnosis is the detection of an immunofluorescence antibody (IFA) in the sample [17]. However, it is not widely present in India at all centers. Therefore, ELISA has been used, which is quite simple, and it is easy to interpret that the results can be obtained in standard laboratories, especially in resource-limited settings.

Our cases were mainly confirmed by serology, blood culture, and urine culture, with the majority (87%) of cases. We also found a significantly lower diagnostic yield for routine investigations that were performed on all patients than for those that were prompted by clinical or laboratory needs. Another reason for the relatively low diagnostic yield of blood cultures in this study might be the previous administration of antibiotics in PC clinics before referral to a tertiary healthcare facility. When considering children with FUO, pediatricians should focus on making the most relevant investigations, where both numbers and costs considerably limit the number of tests. Establishing a specific set of rules for FUO assessment in children at a regional level would be beneficial, and the information obtained in this study can be used for this purpose. Such recommendations could be useful in the pursuit of the best approach for children admitted with fever,

which lasts for over eight days. However, the study has some drawbacks, as it was carried out in a hospital and could not include a larger sample due to time and resource limitations.

Conclusion

Within the limitations of the current study we concluded that infections were the primary cause of FUO in children with enteric fever and scrub typhus being the most frequent diagnosis. Early identification of the cause through specific investigations and appropriate antimicrobial treatment in bacterial diseases will be beneficial. It also shows that there is a requirement for the inclusion of typhoid vaccine in our national immunization schedule. Thus, large-scale multicentre and community-based studies are required to replicate the results of the present study.

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